
Issues of Increasing the Profitability of Commercial Banks

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Abstract: The article discusses the issues of increasing the profitability of commercial banks in the modern world. The main factors affecting the profitability indicators of commercial banks in terms of the downward trend in profitability are considered. Based on the analysis of the dynamics of the banking sector indicators, recommendations are given to increase the profitability of banks, taking into account the current economic situation and the innovative transformation of the financial business.

Key words: commercial bank, profitability, trend, profit indicators, key factors, dynamics of indicators, current economic situation, financial business, innovative transformation.

INTRODUCTION.

The “Strategy for Reforming the Banking System of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2025”, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5992 dated May 12, 2020, establishes the following measures to ensure the financial stability of commercial banks:

gradual exemption from assets and functions that are not inherent in the activities of banks;

development of a national strategy for increasing the accessibility of financial services;

gradual increase in the minimum authorized capital of banks by 2025 to 500 billion soums[1].

It is worth noting that loans account for the largest share in the assets of commercial banks of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Therefore, ensuring the profitability of loans is a necessary condition for ensuring the profitability of bank assets.

Today, the profitability of all commercial banks operating in our country is observed. As evidence of this, the international rating agency Moody's has assigned a "stable" rating to the development prospects of the banking system of Uzbekistan for the sixth consecutive year, the rating agencies Standard & Poor's and Fitch Ratings also assessed the activities of the banking system of Uzbekistan as "stable", and the main indicators of the banking system's activities, such as "total capital adequacy of banks", "liquidity of commercial banks", "dynamics of the volume of deposits", "changes in the volume of credit investments" correspond to high ratings at the end of the reporting year[2].

LITERATURE REVIEW.

According to Prof. J. Sinki, -the net interest margin indicator plays an important role in assessing the income base of commercial banks. The net interest margin is inversely proportional to the amount of bank assets, and the high level of competition in the loan and deposit markets has a strong impact on its level[3]. Here, J. Sinki considers the net interest margin to be the ratio of net interest income to gross assets, and in the banking practice of developed countries, the majority of bank interest income is interest income from loans, and the main part of interest expenses is interest paid on term and savings deposits.

A high and stable share of interest income from loans in the total interest income of commercial banks is a necessary condition for ensuring their financial stability. Therefore, the use of the methodology for calculating the net interest spread coefficient proposed by the experts of the World Bank for Reconstruction and Development in assessing the stability of interest income from loans by banks of our republic, in the author's opinion, is of significant practical importance.

Ensuring the stability of the share of regulatory capital of commercial banks in the volume of liabilities allows to increase the bank's solvency, but this situation may not lead to an increase in its financial stability. Since capital is an expensive source of financing.

According to A. Abdullayev, - in commercial banks of our republic, income from assets is lower than the norm by 0.91 and 0.93 percentage points, and profit is lower by 0.81 and 0.96 percentage points, and these conditions are explained by the fact that commercial banks' resources are not conveniently allocated to income-generating assets[4].

A. Abdullayev's conclusion is somewhat controversial. Because the fact that the income from assets is from 0.81 percent to 0.96 percent compared to the norm is a significantly higher indicator. A. Abdullayev believes that this is not enough. In terms of indicators characterizing the level of income from bank assets and their comparative description, economists have proposed a number of indicators characterizing the income base of commercial banks' assets. However, in the author's opinion, the system of indicators proposed by the IMF to assess the financial stability of commercial banks and including a certain type of financial indicator is of particular importance[4].

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

Mechanisms for increasing the profitability of commercial banks' assets are becoming increasingly important in ensuring financial stability and competitiveness in the modern banking sector. Effective management of bank assets, optimization of the loan portfolio, as well as strategic management of interest rates are the main factors in achieving this goal. Commercial banks are faced with a constantly changing economic environment and increasing competition, which emphasizes the importance of developing and applying effective mechanisms for increasing the profitability of assets.

In today's banking environment, characterized by high competition and rapidly changing market conditions, increasing the profitability of assets is an important strategic task for commercial banks. This thesis discusses the main mechanisms and strategies that banks use to achieve this goal. Particular attention is paid to diversifying the loan portfolio, optimizing interest rates, and reducing transaction costs[5].

Mechanisms for increasing the profitability of commercial banks' assets are a set of strategies, methods, and tools that banks use to increase the profitability of their assets. These mechanisms may include various actions and decisions, such as optimizing the loan portfolio, effectively managing interest rates, reducing transaction costs, developing new financial products and services, and actively participating in the capital market. One of the main mechanisms for increasing the return on assets is the development and implementation of a lending strategy[6]. Banks can analyze the risks and returns of different types of loans and determine the optimal balance between them. This may include allocating a larger share of capital to high-risk but high-return loans, provided that the risk is effectively managed. In addition, banks can actively participate in the securities market and use investments in various assets to increase the profitability of their portfolio[7]. Effective management of interest rates is also an important mechanism for reducing banks' funding costs and increasing profitability.

Reducing transaction costs by automating processes and optimizing the cost structure also helps to increase return on assets. Developing new financial products that meet customer needs can lead to attracting new funds and increasing profitability[8].

It should be noted that successful mechanisms for increasing the return on assets of commercial banks may vary depending on market conditions, strategic objectives and the specific

characteristics of each bank. Therefore, banks are constantly reviewing their business and responding to changes in order to maximize their profits and ensure long-term sustainability.

Improving the mechanisms for increasing the return on assets of commercial banks may include the following key aspects:

Diversity of products and services. Banks can expand their portfolio of products and services by offering a variety of banking products, such as loans, deposits, investment products and insurance. This allows you to attract more customers and diversify sources of income. Effective risk management. Credit risk and other types of risk management play a key role in improving asset profitability[9].

Banks need to develop risk monitoring and assessment strategies to minimize losses and maximize profits.

Optimizing the balance between assets and liabilities. The balance between assets and liabilities plays a key role in determining profitability. Banks can optimize their balance sheets by managing asset size, reducing funding costs, and improving liquidity.

Innovation and technology. Adopting new technologies and innovations, such as digital banking and process automation, can reduce operating costs and improve efficiency, ultimately leading to higher return on assets.

Customer Experience Management. Improving customer experience and customer satisfaction can lead to increased business volume, customer retention, and new customer acquisition.

Diversify and expand markets. Expanding geographic markets and diversifying the business can help reduce dependence on a single market and increase growth potential.

Cost Management. Effectively managing operating expenses and reducing costs can improve margins and return on assets.

Marketing and Sales. Effective marketing and sales strategies help banks attract more customers and sell more profitable products and services.

Market Monitoring. Continuously monitoring market conditions and responding quickly to changes in the economic environment allows banks to identify new opportunities to adapt and increase profitability.

Regulatory Compliance. Compliance with regulations and standards can reduce risks and ensure the stability of bank operations, which is important for increasing the profitability of assets in the long term.

Increase in interest rates on loans. Banks can increase interest rates on loans, which will increase the profitability of assets.

Diversification of assets. The diversity of assets in a bank's portfolio can reduce risks and increase returns. This includes different types of loans, investments and financial products.

Effective credit risk management. Banks should carefully assess and manage credit risks to reduce losses due to non-payment and non-payment of payments.

Increase in lending volume. An increase in the volume of loans issued can increase the profitability of a bank. However, this should be accompanied by careful risk management.

Balance sheet optimization. Banks can optimize their balance sheets to reduce funding costs and increase return on assets.

Innovation in products and services. The development of new financial products and services can create additional sources of income for the bank.

Managing operating costs. Reducing operating costs allows you to increase net income on assets.

Investing in technology. The use of modern technologies, such as robotic process automation and data analytics, allows you to improve the efficiency of bank operations and increase the return on assets.

Optimizing capital levels. Capital management allows the bank to optimize the balance sheet structure and use available capital as efficiently as possible.

Managing interest rates is important. Banks should actively manage the interest rates on their products and services to optimize profitability. Optimizing transaction costs reduces the negative impact on profits[10]. Effective cost management allows banks to increase margins.

Developing new products and services can lead to increased profitability. Innovation and a variety of financial products help attract new customers and increase the volume of assets. Improving credit management helps reduce risk. Effective methods of assessing and monitoring credit risks help to increase the reliability of the loan portfolio.

Banks should introduce modern technologies into their activities to increase efficiency and achieve competitive advantage.

Improving the mechanisms for increasing the profitability of commercial banks allows us to make the following suggestions and recommendations:

Developing more flexible asset management strategies. Banks should constantly review and adapt their strategies depending on changes in market conditions and the economic environment.

Investing in personnel training. Trained employees contribute to more effective asset and risk management.

Cooperation with technology companies and startups. Banks can seek cooperation with innovative companies to introduce the latest technologies into their activities.

Active participation in regulatory issues. Banks should work with regulatory authorities and participate in the formulation of policies that may affect their activities.

Monitoring and analyzing the competitive environment. Banks should constantly analyze the actions of competitors and respond to changes in the market situation.

Focus on customer experience. Improving service quality and creating satisfied customers can lead to more assets. Implementing and utilizing these suggestions and recommendations will help commercial banks increase return on assets and achieve sustainable growth in a dynamic banking sector.

CONCLUSION.

In conclusion, return on assets is a key indicator of the success of banking activities. Banks should constantly strive to increase their return on assets to ensure their financial stability and competitiveness. Diversification of the loan portfolio is an important strategy. Banks can reduce risk by distributing loans among different types of borrowers and sectors of the economy. In general, effective mechanisms for increasing return on assets require flexibility, innovation, and constant adaptation to changing market conditions. Banks that are able to successfully implement these mechanisms will gain an advantage in a competitive market and will be able to achieve sustainable growth and profitability.

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